

Quantifying the U 5*f* covalence and degree of localization in U intermetallics

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A procedure for quantifying the U 5*f* electronic covalency and degree of localization in U intermetallic compounds is presented. To this end, bulk sensitive hard and soft x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy were utilized in combination with density-functional theory (DFT) plus dynamical mean-field theory (DMFT) calculations. The energy dependence of the photoionization cross sections allows the disentanglement of the U 5*f* contribution to the valence band from the various other atomic subshells so the computational parameters in the DFT + DMFT can be reliably determined. Applying this method to UGa₂ and UB₂ as model compounds from opposite ends of the (de)localization range, we have achieved excellent simulations of the valence band and core-level spectra. The width in the distribution of atomic U 5*f* configurations contributing to the ground state, as obtained from the calculations, quantifies the correlated nature and degree of localization of the U 5*f*. The findings permit answering the longstanding question why different spectroscopic techniques give seemingly different numbers for the U 5*f* valence in intermetallic U compounds.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Intermetallic uranium compounds display a plethora of intriguing phenomena including heavy-fermion behavior, unconventional and spin-triplet superconductivity, hidden and multipolar ordering, singlet magnetism, as well as coexistence of ordered phases [1–4]. It is generally accepted that these phenomena originate from the competition and interplay of U 5*f* local atomiclike correlation effects and the tendency of the U 5*f* to delocalize and form bands. The U 5*f*

covalence and degree of localization are hereby key indicators that characterize the system. Yet, the assessment of the electronic structure of these uranium intermetallic compounds is truly challenging since one must go beyond mean-field approaches.

Recent developments based on density functional theory (DFT) combined with dynamical mean field theory (DMFT) provide an exciting opportunity to capture certain aspects of the low- and high-energy properties for a number of U compounds [5–8]. Although achieving very promising results, DFT + DMFT calculations often face the problem of, for example, how to subtract correlation effects already included in both the DFT and the DMFT parts [9] and how to determine the actual magnitude of the correlations. Consequently, accurately reproducing experimentally observed quantities, such as spectra in electron spectroscopy, may pose difficulties if the calculations were to be truly *ab initio*. As a result, the community is facing seemingly conflicting results from different spectroscopic techniques regarding the extent of correlations and the occupation of the 5*f* shell. Examples include the well-known hidden order and unconventional superconductor URu₂Si₂ [10–15], and the recently discovered spin-triplet superconductor UTe₂ [8, 16–23].

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FIG. 1. (a) U M_5 -edge RIXS spectra of UGa_2 as adapted from Ref. [24] and of UB_2 , both measured at resonance energy. The arrows indicate multiplet excitations. (b) HAXPES U 4f core level spectra UGa_2 and UB_2 , after Shirley background subtraction, measured with 6000 eV incident energy. Arrows indicate the satellite structures.

Here we aim to establish a procedure to empirically reduce or even effectively eliminate the uncertainties inherent in DFT + DMFT. Material specific parameters, such as the so-called double counting correction μ_{dc} , the Hubbard U_{ff} , and Hund's J of the U $5f$ states, are obtained by tuning the simulation to accurately reproduce the valence band (VB) spectra that are measured with photoelectron spectroscopy (PES) using different photon energies. Measuring the VB with different photon energies allows enhancing or suppressing contributions of the various subshells because their photoionization cross sections depend differently on the incident energy [25–27]; the U $5f$ states contribute most strongly when the VB is measured with soft x rays whereas they are strongly suppressed in hard x-ray spectra. Having disentangled the spectral weights of the subshells, the parameters in the DFT + DMFT calculation can be optimized.

We consider isostructural UGa_2 and UB_2 as model materials that are at the opposite sides of the localization spectrum. UGa_2 is expected to be more atomiclike, while UB_2 must be more delocalized, as inferred from the U–U distances d_{UU} in their simple AlB_2 hexagonal structure (space group $P6/mmm$) [28–30]. With $d_{\text{UU}} = 4.01 \text{ \AA}$, UGa_2 is well above the Hill limit of 3.5 \AA [31], whereas UB_2 with $d_{\text{UU}} = 3.123 \text{ \AA}$ is well below. The observed high-moment ferromagnetism ($3 \mu_B$) [32,33] in UGa_2 and the paramagnetic properties of UB_2 down to the lowest measured temperature [34] support this assumption. Furthermore, the VB band resonant inelastic x-ray scattering (RIXS) spectra of UGa_2 , measured at the U M_5 edge, exhibit sharp multiplet excitations [see black arrows in Fig. 1(a)]. These excitations were analyzed using a full multiplet approach, which showed that the main configuration is $5f^2$ with Γ_1 and/or Γ_6 symmetry. It was further shown that the large in-plane magnetic moment of UGa_2 is of the induced type, with the Γ_1 singlet being lowest in energy and coupled to the higher-lying Γ_6 doublet [24]. In contrast, the RIXS spectra of UB_2 only show charge transfer scattering, whereas the multiplet excitations are seemingly so strongly broadened that they are no longer distinguishable. Moreover, the U 4f core level spectra obtained with hard x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (HAXPES) exhibit stark differences; in UGa_2 , the main emission lines at 378 and 390 eV binding energy show prominent satellites, while they are barely visible

in the UB_2 core-level data [see black arrows in Fig. 1(b)]. The present core-level data agree well with soft x-ray investigations (see Refs. [35–37] for UGa_2 and Ref. [38] for UB_2). For experimental details of the RIXS and HAXPES data, we refer to Sec. II, Methods, and for further discussion of the spectra we refer to Sec. III, Results, and Sec. IV, Discussion.

This paper aims to provide a quantitative analysis of the charge state of uranium intermetallic compounds. By employing a cross-section guided VB PES study combined with DFT + DMFT calculations, we will determine the charge distribution, the average valence, and the degree of covalence for UGa_2 and UB_2 . Using these results, we will *quantitatively* compute the U 4f core-level spectra. Additionally, we will discuss the presence and absence of multiplet states in the UGa_2 and UB_2 M_5 -edge RIXS spectra, respectively, and address the discrepancies in the interpretation of different spectroscopy techniques concerning the valence states in this material class.

II. METHODS

A. Experiment

UGa_2 single crystals were grown with the Czochralski method and characterized prior to the experiment [39]. Polycrystalline samples of UB_2 were synthesized by arc melting of stoichiometric amounts of crystalline boron (Chempur, 99.95%) together with natural uranium metal (Goodfellow, 99.9%) under a protective atmosphere of Ar gas on a water-cooled copper hearth. The arc-melted sample was placed in an alumina crucible, welded into a tantalum tube and annealed at $1100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 48 hours.

HAXPES measurements were conducted at the P22 beamline [40] at PETRA III (DESY) in Hamburg, Germany. The incident photon energy was set to 6000 eV, thus assuring a higher bulk sensitivity, and photons were detected with a SPECS225HV electron analyzer in the horizontal plane at 90° from the incoming beam, with the sample surface 45° from the incoming beam. Photoelectron spectroscopy with soft x rays (SXPES) was measured with 1200 eV photon energy at the NSRRRC-MPI TPS 45A Submicron Soft X-ray Spectroscopy beamline [41] at the Taiwan Photon Source. Here, the photoelectrons were collected by an MB Scientific

A-1 photoelectron analyzer in the horizontal plane at 60° with sample emission along the surface normal. SX PES with 1486.6 eV photon energy were performed with monochromatized Al $K\alpha$ light in normal emission geometry. Electrons were collected with a Scienta R3000 electron analyzer. In all cases, clean sample surfaces were achieved by cleaving *in situ* in ultrahigh-vacuum condition. The pressures of the main chambers were in the low 10^{-10} mbar range. Valence band spectra of a gold or silver sample were used for calibrating the Fermi level and the overall energy resolution, which was ≈ 230 meV for the 6000 eV, ≈ 200 meV for the 1200 eV and ≈ 300 meV for the 1486.6 eV data. The sample temperature T was kept at 40 K for the 6000 eV and 1200 eV, and at 77 K for the 1486.6 eV measurements.

The RIXS experiments at the U M_5 -edge were performed at Max-Planck IRIXS end station of P01 beamline at Petra III/DESY (Hamburg). The RIXS instrument utilizes hard x-ray optics, as described in Ref. [42], and achieves a resolution of 150 meV at the U M_5 -edge with the 112 reflection of a diced quartz analyzer, as estimated by measuring a carbon tape. The experiment was performed with a scattering angle $2\theta = 90^\circ$ to minimize elastic scattering, a sample angle $\theta_s = 45^\circ$, and $T = 35$ K.

B. Calculations

The valence-band and core-level PES simulations started with a standard DFT + DMFT calculation [43,44] with the local density approximation for the exchange correlation potential. First, the DFT bands for the experimental crystal structure were obtained by the WIEN2K package [45] and subsequently projected onto a tight-binding model spanning U $5f$, $7s$, $6d$ orbitals, Ga $4s$, $4p$, and B $2s$, $2p$ orbitals using the WIEN2WANNIER and WANNIER90 packages [46,47]. The spin-orbit coupling (SOC) was included in the DFT calculation. The tight-binding model was augmented with a local electron-electron interaction within the U $5f$ shell, parameterized by the Hubbard U_{ff} and Hund's J parameters. The strong-coupling continuous-time quantum Monte Carlo (CT-QMC) impurity solver [48–51] was used to compute the U $5f$ self-energy, which was analytically continued to real frequency after the convergence of the DMFT self-consistent loop was achieved [52]. For computational efficiency, only the density-density terms in the Coulomb interaction vertex were taken into account in the CT-QMC calculation. The calculations were performed for $T = 300$ K.

Merging the DFT scheme with DMFT faces the well-known problem of how to avoid double-counting the U $5f$ – $5f$ interaction already present in the DFT results [9,43,53]. To this end, one needs to determine the U $5f$ site energies by subtracting the so-called double-counting correction μ_{dc} from the respective DFT values, but a generally accepted universal expression for μ_{dc} is not available. Practically, μ_{dc} renormalizes the energy splittings between U $5f$ and other uncorrelated orbitals.

By successively varying μ_{dc} in the DFT + DMFT calculations for certain sets of U_{ff} and J , the best agreement of prominent valence-band features in the experimental valence band PES data with the DFT + DMFT spectra determines the μ_{dc} value for the correction. The double-counting dependence

of the valence-band spectra is shown in detail for different sets of U_{ff} and J in Appendix 1.

The core-level PES spectra were calculated from the Anderson impurity model (AIM) augmented with the core states and the real-frequency DFT + DMFT hybridization function discretized into 23 levels (per spin and orbital). For this purpose, we employed the configuration-interaction impurity solver, which allowed us to treat a large number of bath levels (see Refs. [54,55] for details) compared with a standard exact diagonalization solver (see, e.g., Ref. [56]). Nevertheless, treating full U $4f$ core-orbital degrees of freedom was a computationally demanding task. Thus, s -type ($l = 0$) core orbitals were adopted in the AIM, meaning the SOC splitting on the U $4f$ core level and the multipole part in the core-valence (U $4f$ – $5f$) Coulomb interaction were neglected in the spectra. The U $4f_{5/2}$ and $4f_{7/2}$ SOC splitting is large (~ 10 eV) and, consequently, interference effects between the two SOC partners are negligibly small. Thus, only the monopole term U_{fc} in the core-valence interaction had to be adjusted for reproducing the experimental spectra.

III. RESULTS

Figures 2(a)–2(d) show the experimental valence-band PES spectra of UGa₂ and UB₂ measured with soft and hard x-rays. Our low photon energy data agree well with previously reported soft x-ray studies [37,38]. We identify features labeled A to K in the spectra. These features do not shift in energy but exhibit different spectral weights depending on the incident photon energy. In UGa₂, the double peak structure, A (0.15 eV) and B (0.5 eV), is pronounced in the 1200 eV data, while features C (1.11 eV) to F are prominent in the 6000 eV spectrum. It is important to note that feature C has a higher binding energy than feature B. Likewise in UB₂, feature G emerges in the 1486.7 eV data, while the spectral weights of features H to K are enhanced in the 6000 eV dataset.

The energy dependence of the photoionization cross sections [25–27,57] can be exploited to disentangle the different orbital contributions in the valence-band spectra. Figures 3(a) and 3(b) show the photoionization cross sections of the Ga $4s$, Ga $4p$, B $2s$, B $2p$, U $7s$, U $6d$, and U $5f$ orbitals in the soft and hard x-ray energy range, respectively, with the vertical lines signaling the photon energies used in the experiments. The cross sections generally decrease with increasing photon energy, with the U $5f$ one always being the largest. However, in the soft x-ray range, the ratio of the U $5f$ spectral weights to the weights of the other states is at least 3.8 times larger than at 6000 eV. We can thus conclude that the features enhanced in the soft x-ray data, A, B in the UGa₂ spectrum, and G in the UB₂ spectrum, are contributions from U $5f$, while all the other features are due to contributions from non- $5f$ states.

Figures 2(e)–2(h) show the optimized DFT + DMFT calculation for the valence band spectra of UGa₂ and UB₂ after weighing the individual orbital intensities with the respective cross sections in Fig. 3 and after some broadening to mimic the respective experimental resolutions. The parameter values of $U_{\text{ff}} = 3$ eV, $J = 0.59$ eV and $\mu_{\text{dc}} = 4.25$ eV reproduce best all the characteristic valence-band features (A–K) at two photon energies simultaneously [compare to Figs. 2(a)–2(d)]. In Appendix 1, we describe the parameter search and

FIG. 2. (a)–(d) Experimental hard and soft x-ray valence band spectra of UGa_2 and UB_2 measured with 1200 eV, 1486.6 eV, and 6000 eV photon energies. (e)–(h) DFT + DMFT calculations of the valence band spectra of UGa_2 and UB_2 for $U_{\text{ff}} = 3$ eV, $J = 0.59$ eV, and $\mu_{\text{dc}} = 4.25$ eV, after photoionization cross-section corrections (see text) and Gaussian broadening.

demonstrate how the μ_{dc} parameter scales almost linearly with the relative position of the features originating from the U 5*f* states and the features *F* and *K* that come from uncorrelated states. We pick the value of μ_{dc} that fits best the energy position of features *F* and *K* as well as the line shape of the correlated U 5*f* spectrum. The presence of the double-peak features *A* and *B* in the U 5*f* states is a manifest of the sizable Hund's *J* interaction.

The comparison of valence spectra and simulations allows identifying the dominant orbital contributions: features *A*, *B* in Fig. 2(a) and *G* in Fig. 2(c) indeed mainly originate from the U 5*f* states. The intensities *C* and *D* in the spectra of UGa_2 mainly come from the U 6*d* and intensities *E* and *F* from the Ga 4*s* orbitals. For UB_2 features, *H* and *I* are primarily due to the U 6*d*, while features *J* and *K* also have a sizable B 2*s* contribution.

Given the good agreement of the DFT + DMFT calculations with the valence-band experimental spectra, we now assess the U valence. To this end, we resort to a valence histogram on the uranium site, using the DFT + DMFT method with the optimized material specific parameters. These

histograms represent projections of the local density matrix on different 5*f* occupation number sectors. It is computed from the AIM using the numerically exact CT-QMC solver with the DMFT hybridization densities $\Delta(\omega)$. In Figs. 4(a) and 4(b), we present the resulting histograms of UGa_2 and UB_2 . It is evident that numerous 5*f*^{*n*} atomic configurations contribute to the respective ground states of UGa_2 and UB_2 . Thus, the U nominal valence or dominant (starting) configuration for an ionic picture is unclear and is not known *a priori* for U intermetallics. The μ_{dc} shifts the (bare) U 5*f* energy, and thus has a strong effect on the U valence distribution. A smaller μ_{dc} results in a shallower U 5*f* level, thereby leading to smaller fillings. We show the variation of the histograms as a function of μ_{dc} in Appendix 2.

In both histograms of UGa_2 and UB_2 , the U 5*f*² and 5*f*³ configurations are the most prominent. In UGa_2 , the 5*f*¹, *f*², *f*³, and *f*⁴ configurations account for 6%, 66%, 26%, and 2%, respectively, resulting in a filling of the U 5*f* shell of $\langle n \rangle = n_{5f} = 2.24$. In UB_2 , the *f*⁰ and *f*⁵ configurations also contribute. We find 1.7% of *f*⁰, 19.2% of *f*¹, 43.8% of *f*², 28.1% of *f*³, 6.4% of *f*⁴, and 0.6% of *f*⁵, resulting in a filling of $\langle n \rangle = n_{5f} \approx 2.20$. Despite the very different physical properties of UGa_2 and UB_2 , their *average* 5*f* shell fillings are remarkably similar.

The key distinction between the histograms in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b) lies in the width of the distributions. In UGa_2 , the histogram peaks very narrowly around the *f*² configuration, while in UB_2 , the distribution is much broader. The width of the histogram carries information about the magnitude of the charge fluctuations, which we find to be significantly larger in UB_2 . We also add the statistical (binomial) distribution of the charge configurations that correspond to a completely itinerant uncorrelated *f* shell [see red ticks in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b)]. The binomial distribution is given by

$$P(f^n) = \binom{14}{n} (1-c)^{14-n} c^n, \quad (1)$$

where *c* is the electron concentration $c = n_f/14$. [58]. It shows that atomic correlations are not entirely absent in UB_2 because its DFT + DMFT histogram of UB_2 is still not as broad as the binomial distribution. Nevertheless, the distribution is wide enough so the DFT + DMFT results yield only

FIG. 3. Photoionization cross sections of U 5*f*, U 6*d*, U 7*s*, Ga 4*s*, Ga 4*p*, B 2*s*, B 2*p* as interpolated from Refs. [25–27]. The vertical lines indicate the photon energies where the experiments were performed.

FIG. 4. The atomic configuration histograms of the U $5f$ states in UGa₂ (a) and UB₂ (b) calculated by the DFT + DMFT method with optimized parameters, $U_{\text{ff}}=3$ eV, $J=0.59$ eV, and $\mu_{\text{dc}}=4.25$ eV. The red ticks indicate an uncorrelated statistical distribution of atomic configurations (see text). (c) Logarithm of the time-dependent charge correlation functions $\langle \delta n(\tau/\beta) \delta n(0) \rangle$ of UGa₂ and UB₂ calculated by the DFT + DMFT method.

small spectral changes in comparison to the noninteracting DFT results, as shown in Fig. 5.

Above, we inferred the average $5f$ occupation n_{5f} as well as the magnitude of charge fluctuations $\langle \delta n \delta n \rangle$ directly from the histograms. However, charge fluctuations can have rather different origins such as itinerancy, i.e., formation of (broad) bands in intermediate valence systems or the degeneracy of valence states—mixed valence. To distinguish these situations, time-dependent charge correlation functions $\langle \delta n(\tau) \delta n(\tau') \rangle$ must be evaluated [59]. In the former case, the correlation function rapidly decays with time $\tau - \tau'$, while in the latter the correlation function contains a long-lived component (in the limiting case of valence degeneracy of isolated atoms, the correlation function remains constant over time). In Fig. 4(c), we show the local charge-charge correlation

FIG. 5. (a) DFT and (b) DFT + DMFT (with $\mu_{\text{dc}}=4.25$ eV) density of states of UB₂.

function $\langle \delta n(\tau) \delta n(0) \rangle$ in the imaginary time domain for UGa₂ and UB₂. We notice that the value of the function at $\tau = 0$ is larger for UB₂ than for UGa₂, indicating larger charge fluctuations in the former compound. Moreover, the function decays faster in UB₂, suggesting that the charge fluctuations in this compound are primarily due to itinerancy. For a material even more itinerant than UB₂, the charge correlation function would decay even more rapidly over time (and the histogram resembling more the binomial distribution), whereas for a material even more localized than UGa₂, it would eventually become a constant over time (and the histogram becoming even narrower). Such a comparison would be particularly useful for the relative classification of several other intermetallics.

We now turn our attention to the U $4f$ core-level excitations of UGa₂ and UB₂, measured with 6000 eV photon energy, after subtraction of a Shirley-type integral background [see in Fig. 1(b)]. Figures 6(a) and 6(b) display the U $4f_{7/2}$ core-level spectra on an enlarged scale. In the case of UGa₂, a prominent satellite peak is observed at ≈ 6 eV above the main peak. It is important to note that this feature is not present in the U $5f$ spectral weight in the valence-band spectra; see Fig. 2(a). In contrast, the spectrum for UB₂ closely resembles that of an (almost) uncorrelated metal: a main, asymmetric peak is observed with minimal to no satellite structure. We then computed the U $4f$ core-level spectra using the DFT + DMFT AIM [54,55]. The AIM incorporates the DFT + DMFT hybridization densities $\Delta(\omega)$ for the valence-band structure determined above. The sole tuning parameter in this computation is the amplitude of the interaction U_{fc} between the highly localized U $4f$ core hole generated by the x-rays and the $5f$ valence electrons. Figures 6(a) and 6(b) show the calculated spectra for both compounds for three values of U_{fc} .

An excellent reproduction of the energy positions as well as ratios of main and satellite peaks is achieved with $U_{\text{fc}}=5$ eV, which defines this parameters in uranium core-level spectroscopy. It turns out that the core-level data of both compounds are well described with the same set of parameters U_{fc} ,

FIG. 6. U $4f_{7/2}$ core-level HAXPES spectra compared to calculations performed with the DFT + DMFT AIM for different core-valence interaction values U_{fc} , for UGa₂ (a) and UB₂ (b).

U_{ff} , μ_{dc} and J . Hence, the difference in the spectra comes from the larger itinerancy in UB₂, as revealed by the DFT + DMFT calculation. In Appendix 3, we provide a demonstration of the impact of itinerancy on the core-level spectra.

IV. DISCUSSION

The accurate description of the VB as well as U $4f$ core-level spectra lends credibility to the choice of parameters, especially the double counting correction μ_{dc} , in the present DFT + DMFT calculation. Our results show that the U $5f$ electrons in UB₂ are much more itinerant than in UGa₂. Nevertheless, the U $5f^2$ configuration is the most abundant and the average valence ($n_{5f} \approx 2.2$) is almost identical in both compounds. The latter fact shows how treacherous the qualitative interpretation of U $4f$ core-level data in terms of valence can be (see Appendix 3). The M_5 -edge RIXS, on the other hand, do reflect the stronger localization of the $5f$ states in UGa₂ in a very obvious manner: the UGa₂ RIXS data exhibit multiplet excitations, whereas these are washed out for UB₂ due to the significantly larger itinerancy of its $5f$ electrons.

The present results differ from the DFT + DMFT study of UGa₂ by Chatterjee and Kolorenč [56]. Aiming to explain the magnetism, they chose the double-counting parameter μ_{dc} so the $5f$ filling in the DFT + DMFT result is equal to its DFT value. While Chatterjee and Kolorenč also found a double peak structure close to the Fermi energy, the assignment of features B and C , originating from U $5f$ and other states, respectively, is interchanged [see Fig. 2(a)]. In our paper, the assignment is supported by the strong contrast between SX-PES and HAXPES, the latter enhancing the non- $5f$ spectral weights as shown in Fig. 2(b).

Next we will address the issue of conflicting results from different spectroscopic techniques for U intermetallic compounds. Having established the distinct presence of the electronic configurations involved, as well as having determined the magnitude of the electronic correlation energies U_{fc} and U_{ff} , we now are in the position to use the language

of configuration interaction to resolve this issue, thereby highlighting a central aspect in the DMFT approach. The histograms presented in Fig. 4 show that multiple $5f$ valence configurations contribute to the ground state, with $5f^2$ and f^3 carrying the largest weight. Therefore, we focus on these two configurations. How does the U $5f$ mixed valence state with $5f^2$ and f^3 configurations, e.g., as in UGa₂, manifest itself in different spectroscopic techniques and why do different techniques seemingly give different answers?

In the following, we consider two typical core-level spectroscopy cases [60–62]: (1) In processes conserving charge neutrality, such as x-ray absorption (XAS) or nonresonant inelastic x-ray scattering (NIXS) at the $M_{4,5}$, $N_{4,5}$, $O_{4,5}$ edges of uranium, the energy ordering of the states originating from the $5f^2$ and f^3 configurations is the same with (final state) and without (initial state) the core hole. The key parameter for the energy order of the final states is the core-valence interaction U_{fc} , which is comparable to the valence Coulomb interaction U_{ff} . In these charge-neutral processes, where the core-electron excitation takes place locally at the x-ray irradiated site resulting in formation of an exciton, the energy gain attributed to the U_{fc} term is primarily offset by energy loss from the U_{ff} . Thus, the perturbation presented by the x-ray irradiation only slightly renormalizes the energy difference of the underlying ionic configurations. In this case, the spectral weights are *biased* towards the dominant configuration, and thus it should not come as much of a surprise that U $O_{4,5}$ NIXS and M_5 RIXS spectra of UGa₂ have recently been well simulated with an ionic U $5f^2$ model approach [24]. These kinds of methods are mostly sensitive to the main configuration and relevant symmetries of the system. We note that also an atomic $5f^2$ configuration can explain the magnetism in UGa₂ [24,33,63].

(2) Electron removal processes, like PES, promote an inverted order of the ionic configurations in the final state due to the uncompensated core-hole potential U_{fc} . These spectroscopies are characterized by shake-up and satellite structures. In the case of U intermetallics, the spectral weights are determined by both the $5f^2$ and $5f^3$ configurations, making such a spectroscopy truly sensitive to covalence.

As a service to the reader, we provide a simple demonstration of these effects on the spectra in Appendix 3. We construct a simple two-level toy-model for UGa₂, and present the effects of the relevant intra- (U_{ff}) and intershell (U_{fc}) Coulomb interactions on the final state total energy diagram and on the redistribution of spectral weights. We also consider the effect that an increased hopping has on the toy model, so as to mimic a more itinerant system like UB₂. We conclude, the hybridization and covalence effects in U intermetallics are so strong that simple cluster calculations can no longer describe the PES core-level spectra as, e.g., for Ce intermetallic compounds (see, e.g., Refs. [60–62,64,65]). For U intermetallics, the analysis of the PES core-level spectra is no longer intuitive and, as the present paper has shown, requires a full DFT + DMFT-based AIM calculation.

V. CONCLUSION

In summary, we have presented a material-specific DFT + DMFT calculation of two intermetallic model materials, UGa₂ and UB₂, representing the extreme ends of the U $5f$

(de)localization scale. The parameters, Hubbard U_{ff} , Hund's J and, especially, the double counting correction μ_{dc} , were tuned to best reproduce the valence band photoelectron spectroscopy data. Data from different incident photon energies enabled the disentanglement of subshells due to the different energy dependencies of the respective photoionization cross-sections. With the chosen parameters, the satellite structures of the U $4f$ core-level spectra were also well reproduced, requiring only the adjustment of the core-valence interaction U_{fc} . The DFT + DMFT calculation revealed multiple U $5f$ atomic configurations contributing to the ground states of UGa_2 and UB_2 , with the average valence being nearly identical for both compounds. However, the width of the atomic configuration histograms and the time dependence of the charge correlation functions allowed for the assessment of itinerancy; the $5f$ electrons in UB_2 were found to be much more itinerant than in UGa_2 . This paper paves the way to a systematic classification of uranium intermetallic compounds: it establishes an experiment-guided DFT + DMFT quantitative assessment of the charge state in this class of materials, as well as a quantitative simulation of the U $4f$ core-level spectra based on the Anderson impurity model coupled to the DFT + DMFT hybridization function. We argue that different spectroscopic techniques should yield consistent results for the charge state of uranium in intermetallics and that the key ingredient is the proper inclusion of the electron correlation effects at the U sites relative to the itinerancy.

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APPENDIX

1. Finding U_{ff} , J and μ_{dc} with valence band spectra

Figure 7 summarizes the parameter dependence of the DFT + DMFT valence-band spectra for UGa_2 . Analogous arguments can be made for UB_2 . The gray vertical lines indicate the valence-band features (A to F) in the experimental PES data, see Figs. 2(a) and 2(b). We used 2.0 eV and 0.59 eV

as starting values for Hubbard U_{ff} and Hund's J , respectively, values that were used in the DFT + DMFT study of Chatterjee and Kolorenč [56]. The J value corresponds to 80% of the Hartree-Fock value of the U $5f^3$ configuration [66]. Around these U_{ff} and J values, we performed DMFT valence-band calculations for an extensive range of the double-counting correction μ_{dc} values. For a given set of U_{ff} and J , the μ_{dc} parameter controls the energy difference between U $5f$ and uncorrelated states. Thus, in the calculation, the energy positions that correspond to, e.g., the Ga $4s$ features E and F are almost linearly shifted to higher binding energies with increasing μ_{dc} .

The double-counting correction μ_{dc} , however, depends on the choice of U_{ff} and J values because it is intended to subtract the electron-electron interaction effects present in the DFT result on the mean-field level. Thus, in Fig. 7, the μ_{dc} -dependent spectra for different sets of U_{ff} and J are arranged in a matrix manner, such that in each row the calculated F feature appears at a similar binding energy. This demonstrates that one can find values for μ_{dc} that reproduce the high-energy valence-band features for any set of U_{ff} and J . However, the choice of U_{ff} and J affects the U $5f$ features through the f - f interaction. It is important to note for $U_{\text{ff}} = 3.0$ eV and $J = 0.59$ eV additional good agreement with the experimental U $5f$ features A and B is obtained.

2. μ_{dc} dependence of the atomic configuration histograms

Figure 8 shows the variation of the atomic configuration histograms of UGa_2 and UB_2 with μ_{dc} . The double-counting correction renormalizes the energy position of the U $5f$ states, thus having a large impact on the valence distribution. This is particularly evident for UGa_2 , where the distribution is very narrow for a shallower U $5f$, e.g., for $\mu_{\text{dc}}=3.50$ eV, the $5f^2$ configuration strongly dominates (73.7%), while for deeper $5f$ states, e.g., for $\mu_{\text{dc}}=5$ eV, the f^2 and f^3 configurations contribute almost equally to the ground state.

3. Toy model for comparing core-level PES and XAS

We consider a two-level *initial state* Hamiltonian \hat{H} consisting of f^2 and $|f^3\bar{L}\rangle$ configurations, with \bar{L} representing a valence hole. The two levels are separated by the charge transfer energy Δ and are coupled by the hopping amplitude t [see initial Fig. 9(a)] [60–62]. In the toy model,

$$\hat{H} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & t \\ t & \Delta \end{pmatrix},$$

the ground state $|g\rangle = \alpha|f^2\rangle + \beta|f^3\bar{L}\rangle$ with coefficients α and β is determined by ratio t/Δ . We select $t/\Delta=0.822$, resulting in the average $5f$ occupation $n_{5f} = 2.24$ for UGa_2 and UB_2 that was obtained in the main text, with α^2 and β^2 amounting to 0.76 and 0.24, respectively.

In the following, two cases will be discussed: (1) How U_{fc} , for a fixed choice of t and Δ , and fixed ratio of $U_{\text{ff}}/U_{\text{fc}}$ in the case of XAS, impacts the satellites in core-level PES and XAS. (2) How t and Δ , for the same ratio $t/\Delta=0.822$ and a given set of U_{ff} and U_{fc} , impact the core level satellite in PES and XAS.

Case (1): The final states of the core-level PES and XAS processes are characterized by the presence of a core hole,

FIG. 7. U_{ff} and μ_{dc} dependence of the DFT + DMFT valence band spectra of UGa_2 . The vertical lines denote the energy position of the experimental features A–F, see labeling at top of figure and compare to Figs. 2(a) and 2(b). The panels with the optimal value of the parameters fitting the experimental spectra are marked by a frame and show the same calculation as Figs. 2(e) and 2(f).

necessitating consideration of the core-valence interaction U_{fc} between a core hole (c) and $5f$ valence electrons.

In the PES *final state*, charge neutrality is broken. The basis is formed by $|cf^2\rangle$ and $|cf^3L\rangle$ and the Hamiltonian \hat{H}_{PES} reads

$$\hat{H}_{PES} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & t \\ t & \Delta - U_{fc} \end{pmatrix}.$$

In the final state, the configurations $|cf^3L\rangle$ and $|cf^2\rangle$ are separated by $\Delta - U_{fc}$ [see *final state PES* in Fig. 9(a)] and red and green ticks in the left panel of Fig. 9(b). Choosing $\Delta = 1.75$ eV with $t = 1.4373$ eV, maintaining the ratio $t/\Delta = 0.822$, we calculate the core-level spectra for several values of U_{fc} between

0 and 6 eV [see left panel of Fig. 9(b)]. The exercise shows the sensitivity of peak positions and intensity ratios to U_{fc} for a given t and Δ . For $U_{fc} = 0$, the energy separation of the red and green ticks is given by Δ . With increasing U_{fc} , the levels eventually cross when $\Delta - U_{fc}$ becomes negative, i.e., the order of configurations is reversed with respect to the initial state. For $U_{fc} = 5$ eV [see blue curve in Fig. 9(b)], the value used in the present DFT + DMFT calculations, the toy model mimics the strong satellite of the $4f_{7/2}$ PES spectrum of UGa_2 in Fig. 6. With U_{fc} larger than Δ , the order of states is thus reversed in UGa_2 . We note that this is actually a typical situation for the core-level spectra of f electron materials.

FIG. 8. μ_{dc} dependence of the atomic configuration histograms of UGa_2 (top) and UB_2 (bottom), where $U_{ff} = 3$ eV and $J = 0.59$ eV. The panels with the optimal value of the parameters fitting the experimental spectra are marked by a frame and show the same data as Figs. 4(a) and 4(b).

The relative spectral weights in the final state are not equal to the relative abundances β^2 and α^2 in the initial state. The transfer of spectral weight originates from the superposition (quantum-mechanical interference) of the f^2 - and f^3 -derived states in both the initial and final states. Therefore, the PES spectra cannot be modeled with an f^2 ionic model, even though the f^2 dominates the initial state. The reversed order of the configurations in the final state leads to substantial redistribution of spectral intensities. Only in the limit of very large U_{fc} or very small t would the PES intensities correspond to the weights of the initial state configurations. However, for uranium intermetallics both covalence and Coulomb interaction must be treated on the same footing.

For the charge neutral process in XAS, the basis is formed by $|cf^3\rangle$ and $|cf^4L\rangle$, and the Hamiltonian \hat{H}_{XAS} reads

$$\hat{H}_{XAS} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & t \\ t & \Delta - U_{fc} + U_{ff} \end{pmatrix}.$$

For the $|cf^4L\rangle$ configuration, the energy gain due to U_{fc} is compensated by the extra f - f Coulomb repulsion U_{ff} due to the extra (photoexcited) f electron [see *final state XAS* in Fig. 9(a)]. Typically, U_{fc} is larger than U_{ff} , but they are of the same order of magnitude. Thus, in XAS, the levels in the final state have the same order as in the initial state, unlike in PES [see red and green ticks in right panel of Fig. 9(b)].

FIG. 9. (a) Schematic energy diagram displaying the initial state problem with ground state $|g\rangle = \alpha|f^2\rangle + \beta|f^3L\rangle$, and PES and XAS final states. (b) Core-level (c) PES and XAS spectra in the two-configuration toy model, maintaining the same average $5f$ filling, for various core-valence interaction values U_{fc} and a fixed small hopping t (and small Δ) addressing the UGa_2 electronic structure problem (see blue spectrum). (c) Core-level PES and XAS spectra in the two-configuration toy model, maintaining the same average $5f$ filling, for several values of hopping t (and Δ) with fixed $U_{fc}=5$ eV, addressing the problem of UB_2 (see gray spectrum). The red and green ticks mark the energy positions of the nonhybridized final states.

We fix the parameter U_{ff} to $U_{fc}/1.3$ and then calculate the XAS spectra for several values of U_{fc} between 0 and 6 eV [see Fig. 9(b)]. The main line and satellite are composed largely of $|cf^3\rangle$ and $|cf^4L\rangle$, respectively, with the main line consistently dominating the spectrum, despite the mixture of f^2 and f^3 in the initial state. Hence, XAS spectra reflect the dominant f^2 configuration. In contrast to PES, the satellites are never very large and peak positions and intensities are fairly insensitive to U_{fc} . In case $U_{ff}=U_{fc}$, the satellite intensity would even be zero for all values of U_{fc} .

Therefore, an ionic model considering only the formal f^2 configuration provides a valid description for core-level XAS (similarly for NIXS) in uranium intermetallic compounds.

Case (2): Now, we discuss the impact of t and Δ with a fixed t/Δ of 0.822 to maintain the same $5f$ occupation. We now fix $U_{fc}=5$ eV and vary t (and Δ) from 1.437 eV, the value mimicking the case of UGa_2 [see blue curve in Fig. 9(c)], to $t=4.5$ eV. Again, we observe a strong dependence of position and intensity ratios on the actual size of t (and Δ). The hopping of $t=3.5$ eV mimics the PES core-level data of UB_2 [see gray curve in Fig. 9(c)]. For even larger values of t (and Δ), the satellite becomes even smaller and the order of states reverses back to the same order as in the initial state. In XAS, as before, the spectra exhibit only one major line and a negligible satellite spectral weight, the latter becoming even less pronounced the larger Δ becomes with respect to U_{fc} and U_{ff} .

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